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Corporate Social Responsibility And Financial Performance Of Listed Manufacturing Firms In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of corporate social responsibility and financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. However, the specific objectives were to: evaluate the effect of environmental responsibility, social responsibility, staff welfare and economic responsibility on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *Ex-post facto* research design was adopted, and panel data covering ten (10) years (2014-2023) were collected across twenty five (25) selected manufacturing firms in Nigeria which formed the sample size of the study. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and panel multiple regression analysis via E-views 10.0 statistical package. The study findings revealed that environmental responsibility has a non-significant negative effect (Coeff. =-0.0040{0.6262}) on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria; Social responsibility has a non-significant positive effect (Coeff. =0.0043{0.1605}) on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria; Economic responsibility has a significant positive effect (Coeff. =0.0073{0.0226}) on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria and Staff welfare responsibility has a significant positive effect (Coeff. =0.0123{0.0103}) on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. It was concluded that environmental responsibility has a non-significant negative effect on return on assets, while social responsibility has a non-significant positive effect. However, economic responsibility and staff welfare responsibility have significant positive effects on return on assets. It was recommended that Firms should review their environmental responsibility initiatives and consider alternative approaches that may be more effective in improving financial performance and Policymakers and regulatory bodies in Nigeria should encourage listed manufacturing firms to disclose their social responsibility initiatives more transparently. Improved disclosure of social responsibility initiatives can help stakeholders better understand the impact of these initiatives and make more informed investment decisions.

Keywords: corporate social responsibility, financial performance, manufacturing firms

INTRODUCTION

Corporate social responsibility has become an integral part of the business landscape worldwide, with companies increasingly recognizing the importance of their social and environmental impact. The practice of CSR activities has gained significant attention as a means for organizations to demonstrate their commitment to ethical business practices (Adesunloro et al., 2019). Nigeria, as one of Africa's largest economies, is experiencing rapid industrial growth, particularly in the manufacturing sector. As cited in Oyewumi et al., (2018) the industrial goods firms listed on the Nigerian exchange group play a crucial role in driving economic development, employment generation, and technological advancement. However, this has also raised concerns regarding the potential negative externalities associated with industrial activities, such as pollution, waste generation, and resource depletion as opined by Akinbode et al., (2021).

According to Aliyu (2018), corporate social responsibility is a key tool for achieving effective communication of a company's social and environmental responsibility activities to stakeholders. It entails the process of communicating the social and environmental effects of organizations' economic actions to particular groups within society and to

society at large (Oyewumi & Afolabi, 2019). By so doing, companies inform their stakeholders on the extent to which they have responded to social and environmental concerns through such media of disclosure as annual reports; advertisement or articles published detailing a company's activities; booklets to address the social activities of the company; community development reports; environmental reports; labelling of products to promote environmental and other concerns; press releases; supplement to the annual reports produced at interim dates; video tapes and websites (Konar & Cohen, 2001).

Annual report, therefore, has unique characteristic of being the obvious place of signaling disclosures and the only medium over which corporate management has complete editorial control (Afolabi & Ajayi, 2017). Moreover, Adelopo et al., (2020) opined that corporate social responsibility forms a central charter for public relations in communicating and creating mutual understanding, managing potential conflicts and achieving legitimacy. This comprise of mandatory and voluntary reporting. Mandatory reporting discloses information as required by law while voluntary reporting is not regulated but discloses information that is nonetheless, useful to stakeholders. Corporate social responsibility is an example of voluntary reporting since it differs significantly from financial and operational disclosures (Adelopo et al., 2020). While accounting standards bodies and capital markets regulate mandatory disclosures, companies make their own decisions as far as voluntary disclosure is concerned. So far, progress has been made and there is room for improvement in terms of the quality and depth of CSR. Efforts towards comprehensive and meaningful reporting builds stakeholder's confidence which ultimately contributes to sustainable development in Nigeria's industrial sector.

According to Ihendinihu et al., (2016), Corporate Social Responsibility therefore, means that companies in the cause of discharging their day-to-day activities for the purpose of profit realization should also take into consideration the effect of their activities on the members of the society in which the companies are residing and the environmental sustainability of their operations. The origin of Corporate Social Responsibility in the Nigerian context can be traced back to the period of unbridled of oil in the southern part of Nigeria (South-South Geo-Political Zone). The discovery of the oil brought a serious conflict between the companies and the host environment (Elkington, 2010). On one hand, members of the community are complaining of environmental degradation that led to various types of hardships and on the other, the companies are not willing to accept that they are the major cause of the hardships. These conflicts of interest led to the emergence and implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility. It protects human rights against corporate abuses and also recognizes the interests of the public and thus, various legislations designed to regulate business and industry in Nigeria (Gunu, 2008).

In response to the demands of society at the present time along with promoting the interests of companies with all their activities via improving their social responsibility roles companies apply social responsibility accounting for realizing these objectives and also to respond to such expectations. The traditional concern of business organizations which was to focus on strategies for business operations and to maximize profit through diversification, product differentiation and globalization has been undermined overtime. The evolution of strategic thinking therefore underscores the need to include activities that seek to integrate social and environmental issues into business decision making process. In addition, companies in recent years are facing increasing pressures from their stakeholders to address and disclose social and environmental responsibilities. As a result, the need for Corporate Social Responsibility has increased over the years. Elkington, (1997) notes that "Corporate Social Responsibility has been developed to extend the traditional model of financial reporting, which emphasizes a firm's economic prosperity to accommodate social and environmental dimensions."

The return on assets ratio (ROA) often called the return on total asset, is a profitability ratio that measures the net income produced by total assets during a period by comparing net income to the average total assets. In other words, the return on assets ratio or ROA measures how efficiently a company can manage its assets to produce profits during a period (Konar & Cohen, 2011). According to Gunu (2008), "companies are responsible for all their stakeholders and should therefore take greater responsibility for the society at large and seek to solve social and environmental problems in their market place." Ainscough et al., (2007) opined that, "Corporate Social Responsibility is the economic, legal, moral, and philanthropic actions of firms that influence the quality of life of relevant stakeholders." Crowther, (2000) described Corporate Social Responsibility as "the voluntary disclosures of information, both qualitative and quantitative, made by organizations to inform or influence a range of audiences. The quantitative disclosures may be in financial or non-financial terms."

In Nigeria, the implementation and recognition of social reporting is comparatively new, but it has become prominent in some accounting reports today (Akinlo & Iredele, 2014). The concept is given attention now due to the increasing hazards such as disruption of business activities by host communities, abuse of workers, kidnapping of workers occasioned by the various companies in the country. Although most companies, especially those listed on the Nigerian exchange group disclose social reporting activities in their annual reports to show that they are socially

responsible, but there are still agitations by host communities that companies are not socially responsible to them. These agitations most times come with hostility such as kidnapping, destruction, and assaults, especially in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria; and these have made some firms to cease business operations in these regions (Omodero & Ihendinihu, 2016).

The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of corporate social responsibility on financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. However, the specific objectives were to:

1. Evaluate the effect of environmental responsibility on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
2. Analyze the effect of social responsibility on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
3. Ascertain the effect of economic responsibility on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
4. Access the effect of staff welfare responsibility on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual framework

The conceptual relationships among the variables are depicted in figure 2.1 below;

Corporate Social Responsibility Financial Performance

Fig 2.1: Interrelationships of variables
Source: Researcher’s conceptualization (2024)

Corporate social responsibility

A business enterprise is an important part of the society and it should do its operations and earn money in ways that satisfy the expectations of the society. Social responsibility of a business refers to the obligations to take those decisions and perform those actions which are desirable in terms of the objectives and values of society. It is the idea that businesses should balance profit-making activities with activities that benefit society; it involves developing businesses with a positive relationship with the society in which they operate (Dukes, 2002).

Corporate social responsibility is concerned with the measurement and disclosure of costs and benefits to the society as a result of operating activities of a business enterprise. Thus, social accounting measures social costs and social benefits as a result of business activities for communication to various groups both within and outside the business (Maheshwari, 2013). Wason (2006), defined Social responsibility accounting as that part of accounting concerned with the process of identification, measurement and communicating the contribution made by the business enterprise to the society in which the business enterprise is born and thereafter grow. Aliyu, (2018) sees social accounting as the “process of communicating the social and environmental effects of organizations’ economic actions to particular interest groups within society and to society at large.

Environmental Responsibility

Environmental responsibility initiatives are aim at reducing pollution and greenhouse gas emissions, and the sustainable use of natural resources. Currently, we need to focus on two main areas of our environment: limiting pollution and reducing greenhouse gases. Companies are bound to fulfill their economic responsibility because awareness of environmental issues is growing largely among the consumers and today, they want businesses to take

necessary steps to save our planet and preserve all the lives in it. Companies that are concerned about reducing air, land, and water pollution have increased their standing as good corporate citizens while benefiting society. Environmental responsibility cannot be shy away from environmental accounting.

Environmental accounting is defined as the identification, compilation, estimation and analysis of environmental costs information for better decision-making within the firm and which helps managers fulfill corporate environmental objectives (Tibor, 1996) as in (Akabom, 2012). It can also be defined as “the generation, analysis, and the use of financial and non-financial information in order to optimize corporate, environmental and economic performance, achieving a sustainable business (Bennett & James, 1998). The ultimate objective of environmental responsibility is to clearly indicate the environmental cost of each process, separating the non-environmental costs from the environmental costs.

Environmental responsibility covers information relating to all aspects of the environment. It includes environment-related expenditure, environmental benefits of products and details regarding sustainable operations (Tibor, 1996). According to the world conservative union, consumption of natural capital- the depletion of natural capital - forests, in particular - is accounted for as income. Thus, the accounts of a country which harvests trees very quickly will show quite high income for a few years, but nothing will show the destruction of a productive asset, the forest. Whereas in accordance with conventional business accounting principles, the gradual depletion of physical capital- machines and other equipment – are treated as depletion rather than income. However, most experts on environmental disclosure agree that the depletion of natural capital should be accounted for in the same way as other productive assets.

Economic Responsibility

Economic responsibility initiatives involve improving the firm’s business operation while participating in sustainable practices – for example, using a new manufacturing process to minimize wastage. Economic responsibility is an interconnected field that focuses to strike a balance between business, environmental, and philanthropic practices. Economic responsibility abides by, the set standards of ethical and moral regulations. In this context, companies try to find out a solution that can facilitate their business growth and generate profits by benefitting the community and our society (Hidayat, 2017).

Economic responsibility encompasses a wide array of facets that manufacturing firms in Nigeria need to consider and address. Firstly, it involves maintaining financial prudence and transparency in their operations, ensuring that they comply with relevant financial regulations and standards, and generating consistent profits to sustain their business operations and investments. This aspect is crucial not only for the firm's own financial health but also for attracting and retaining investors who seek stable returns on their investments (Aliyu, 2018).

Economic responsibility entails creating economic value not just for shareholders but also for employees, suppliers, customers, and the community at large. This can be achieved through fair wages and benefits for employees, fostering strong relationships with suppliers based on ethical sourcing practices, providing high-quality products and services to customers, and contributing to local economic development initiatives (Gull et al., 2023). By prioritizing these aspects, manufacturing firms can enhance their reputation, build trust with stakeholders, and drive long-term financial success.

Staff Welfare Responsibility

In corporate social responsibility (CSR), staff welfare responsibility refers to a company’s commitment to ensuring the well-being, health, and safety of its employees. This disclosure includes information about the various initiatives and programs that the company has implemented to support its staff members, such as health and wellness benefits. Safety protocols, training and development opportunities, work-life balance initiatives, and employee assistance programs (Yan et al., 2021). By exploring their staff welfare responsibilities, companies demonstrate their commitment to creating a positive work environment and fostering a culture of care and support for their employees. This transparency not only helps build trust with stakeholders but also showcases the company’s efforts to prioritize the welfare of its staff members as part of its CSR strategy.

Staff welfare responsibility is viewed from different perspectives and angles. The perspectives vary from individual authors to organizations and as a result there is no generally accepted unified definition of the concept. But, on critically viewing the various definitions given one could observe that they are centered on three themes as stated by Crowther (2000). These themes are corporate relations to economic, societal and environmental sustainability. It is on this basis that several terms like corporate conscience, good corporate citizenship, business responsibility, business citizenship, social performance, sustainable responsible business, community relations, and responsible business are used to connote staff welfare reporting.

Social Responsibility

Substantial effort and resources have been deplored to ensure that our natural environment is not treated as a free well (Tapang et al., 2012). Social reporting has an instrumental role in disclosing environmental responsibility for different entities whether industrial, commercial service and at all levels whether micro or macro. Thus, social reporting became concerned with achieving new goals such as measuring and evaluating potential or actual environmental impacts of projects and organizations. These new goals are of great importance as they enable many users to take different development decisions that are economically and environmentally sound (Bala & Yusuf, 2003). Freeman (1983) identified the main reasons of accounting interest in the environment as follows; many environmental costs can be significantly reduced eliminated as a result of business decisions, ranging from operational and housekeeping changes to investment in cleaner production, to redesign of processes/products. Environmental cost (and, thus potential cost savings) may be obscured in overhead accounts or otherwise overlooked.

Many organizations have discovered that environmental costs can be offset in generating revenues through sales of waste by products for example: Accounting for environmental cost and performance can support an organization's development and operating in an overall environmental management system (EMS) and 150 14000 accreditations. Environmental expenditures whether capital (CAPEX) or operating costs (OPEX) increase dramatically day after day.

Management needs financial data about these expenditures. For strategic cost leadership (Driving Cost). There is need to prioritize these expenditures. There are increasing needs from different stakeholders (government, investors, lenders, banks, non-governmental organizations.) to have financial data on the environmental performance of different organization. If accounting does not provide financial data on the environmental performance of organizations that will help non-complying organizations/entities to pollute environment and spoil resources and yet appear more economic efficient than others that incur costs to protect the environment. Naturally any entity has a main output and a secondary-output of which mainly pollutes and thus if the entity does not incur costs to mitigate or prevent it a third party in the society have to bear it (the concept of externality).

Financial Performance

Company performance is very essential to management as it's an outcome which has been achieved by an individual or group of individuals in organization related to its authority and responsibility in achieving the goal legally, not against the law, and conforming to the morale and ethic.

Firm Financial performance may be defined as the ability of an organization to accomplish certain objectives. According to Fubara (2004) performance refers to a number of a different aspect. To management, successful means achieving company's objectives, profit, growth, market share etc. satisfying customer's expectations – price, quality, quantity, time etc. and satisfying the needs of workforce – good pay, satisfaction etc. although, performance criteria may differ according to the type of product or service, generally it involves effective use of resources to efficiently convert inputs into the required outputs at the right cost, quality, time and space. Firm financial performance reflects business outcome and results achieved towards the firms predetermined objectives.

Firm financial performance is measured in relation to established organization objectives. Management expert Dukes (2002), Freeman (1983), has stated that objectives should be established in at least areas of organizational performance. Market standing innovations, productivity, physical, and financial resources, profitability, manager performance and responsibility, worker performance and attitude and social responsibility.

Return on Asset (ROA)

The return on assets ratio, often called the return on total asset, is a profitability ratio that measures the net income produced by total assets during a period by comparing net income to the average total assets. In other words, the return on assets ratio or ROA measures how efficiently a company can manage its assets to produce profits during a period.

Since company assets' sole purpose is to generate revenues and produce profits, this ratio helps both management and investors see how well the company can convert its investments in assets into profits. In short, this ratio measures how profitable a company's assets are. The return on assets ratio is calculated by dividing net income by average total assets.

The relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance

The relationship between CSR and CFP has been empirically examined by many studies. In early study, Griffin and Mahon summarized the findings of various articles and concluded that no conclusive consensus exists on the empirical on CSR and CFP. In another studies using a meta-analysis clone by Ali et al., (2002) and Freeman (1983) in the United Kingdom (I.1K) show that CSR has a positive impact on CFP. Likewise, Gull et al. (2023) used an average of 524 annual reports of the large United States (US) corporations for the period of 1991-1996. Regression

model was adopted as measure of CFP (dependent variable) while social performance, industry and expenditure for research and development was adopted as CSR measures (independent variables). The findings suggest that inclusion of research and development variables in the model caused CSR variable to be insignificant, leading them to the conclusion that there is no relationship between CSR and firm financial performance if the regression model is properly specified.

The study revealed that the level of CSR disclosure among GLCs is high as the trend of disclosure among social information is increasing from 1 year to another throughout the period of the study. However, the statistical result indicates that not all the CSR activities were found to be correlated with CFP. Only environment theme has a positively and weak correlation with the ROA. It can be concluded that although, the positive relation between CSR and CFP has prevailed in many studies but still the results remain inconclusive. Such, inconclusiveness creates ground for further research. The trend in developed markets show there has been widespread empirical study on the relationship between CSR and CFP.

Effect of environmental responsibility on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms

Environmental responsibility covers information relating to all aspects of the environment. It includes environment-related expenditure, environmental benefits of products and details regarding sustainable operations (Tibor, 1996). According to the world conservative union, consumption of natural capital - the depletion of natural capital - forests, in particular - is accounted for as income. Thus, the accounts of a country which harvests trees very quickly will show quite high income for a few years, but nothing will show the destruction of a productive asset, the forest. Whereas in accordance with conventional business accounting principles, the gradual depletion of physical capital - machines and other equipment - are treated as depletion rather than income.

However, most experts on environmental disclosure agree that the depletion of natural capital should be accounted for in the same way as other productive assets. Yakhou and Dorweiler, (2003) specified that Environmental accounting is an inclusive field of accounting. It provides reports for both internal use generating environmental information to help make management decisions on pricing, controlling overhead and capital budgeting, and external use, disclosing environmental information of interest to the public and to the financial community. Implementing environmentally responsible practices such as energy efficiency, waste reduction, and sustainable sourcing can lead to cost savings in the long run. By reducing energy consumption, waste disposal costs, and raw material expenses, a company can improve its profitability and hence ROA. Embracing environmental responsibility often involves optimizing processes and operations to be more resource-efficient. This can lead to improved overall efficiency, productivity, and utilization of assets, all of which can positively impact ROA.

Effect of social responsibility on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms

Substantial effort and resources have been deployed to ensure that our natural environment is not treated as a free well (Tapang et al., 2012). Social reporting has an instrumental role in disclosing environmental responsibility for different entities whether industrial, commercial service and at all levels whether micro or macro. Thus, social reporting became concerned with achieving new goals such as measuring and evaluating potential or actual environmental impacts of projects and organizations. These new goals are of great importance as they enable many users to take different development decisions that are economically and environmentally sound (Bala & Yusuf, 2003). Companies that are socially responsible often enjoy a positive reputation among consumers, which can lead to increased customer loyalty and higher sales. This can ultimately lead to higher revenues and improved profitability, positively impacting ROA. Companies that actively address social issues and adopt sustainable practices are often better equipped to manage risks related to regulatory compliance, reputational damage, and supply chain disruptions. By minimizing these risks, the company can protect its assets and enhance its financial performance.

Effect of Economic Responsibility On Return On Assets Of Listed Manufacturing Firms

Economic responsibility encompasses a wide array of facets that manufacturing firms in Nigeria need to consider and address. Firstly, it involves maintaining financial prudence and transparency in their operations, ensuring that they comply with relevant financial regulations and standards, and generating consistent profits to sustain their business operations and investments. This aspect is crucial not only for the firm's own financial health but also for attracting and retaining investors who seek stable returns on their investments (Aliyu, 2018). Economic responsibility entails creating economic value not just for shareholders but also for employees, suppliers, customers, and the community at large. This can be achieved through fair wages and benefits for employees, fostering strong relationships with suppliers based on ethical sourcing practices, providing high-quality products and services to customers, and contributing to local economic development initiatives (Gull et al., 2023). By prioritizing these aspects, manufacturing firms can enhance their reputation, build trust with stakeholders, and drive long-term financial success. Regularly analyze the company's ROA to understand how effectively it is utilizing its assets to

generate profits. Track the trend over time and compare it with industry benchmarks to assess performance. Firms should work closely with other stakeholders within the organization, such as finance, operations, and management teams, to align strategies and goals that contribute to improving ROA.

Effect of staff welfare responsibility on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms

Staff welfare responsibility is viewed from different perspectives and angles. The perspectives vary from individual authors to organizations and as a result there is no generally accepted unified definition of the concept. But, on critically viewing the various definitions given one could observe that they are centered on three themes as stated by Crowther (2000). These themes are corporate relations to economic, societal and environmental sustainability. It is on this basis that several terms like corporate conscience, good corporate citizenship, business responsibility, business citizenship, social performance, sustainable responsible business, community relations, and responsible business are used to connote staff welfare reporting.

The concept is therefore closely linked to the principle of sustainability, which argues that enterprises should make decisions based not only on financial factors such as profits and dividends, but also based on the immediate and long term social and environmental consequences of their activities (Gullet et al., 2023). In the view of Fubara (2004), it is described as the ability of company to link itself with ethical values, transparency. Employee relations. Compliance with legal requirements and overall respect for the communities in which they operate. Providing a positive work environment and supporting staff welfare initiatives can boost employee morale and foster a sense of teamwork. This can lead to better collaboration, communication, and overall performance, all of which can positively impact ROA. Happy and satisfied employees are more likely to provide better customer service, leading to increased customer satisfaction and loyalty. This can result in higher sales and repeat business, ultimately contributing to a higher ROA. Companies that prioritize staff welfare and demonstrate a commitment to their employees' well-being often enjoy a positive reputation and brand image. This can attract top talent, customers, and investors, all of which can positively influence the company's financial performance and ROA.

Theoretical framework

The researcher used a number of theories to contextualize the study by adopting the following literatures and theories:

Stakeholders Theory by Edward Freeman in 1984

This theory was propounded by Edward Freeman in 1984. The basic proposition of the stakeholders' theory is that the firm's success is dependent upon the successful management of all the relationships that a firm has with its stakeholders –a term originally introduced by Stanford research institute (SRI) to refer to those groups without whose support the organization would cease to exist (Freeman 1983). Freeman's stakeholders' theory asserts that, managers must satisfy a variety of constituents (example, employees, customers, suppliers, local community and so on) who can influence the firm's outcomes. According to this view, it is not sufficient for managers to focus exclusively on the needs of stakeholders, or the owners of the business. This implies that it can be beneficial for the firm to engage in certain environmental activities that non-financial stakeholders perceive important, because without this, these groups might withdraw their support from the business.

In developing the stakeholder theory, Freeman, (1983) incorporates the stakeholders' concept into categories: A business planning and policy model, and A corporate social responsibility model of stakeholder management. In the first model, the stakeholder analysis focuses on developing and evaluating the approval of corporate strategy decisions by groups whose support is required for the firm's continued existence. The stakeholders identified in the model include the owners, customers, public groups and suppliers. Although these groups are not adversarial in nature, their possibly conflicting behavior is considered a constant on the strategy developed by management to best match their firm's resources with the environment (Akinlo and Iredele, 2014). In the second model, the corporate planning and analysis extends to include external influences which may be adversarial to the firm. These adversarial groups may include the regulatory environmentalist and /or special interest groups concerned with social issues (Idemudia & Ite, 2006).

The second, model enables managers and accountants to consider a strategic plan that is adaptable to change in the social demands of non-traditional stakeholders' groups. The stakeholders' theory proposed an increased level of environmental awareness which creates the need for companies to extend their corporate planning to include the non-traditional stakeholders like the regulatory adversarial groups in order to adapt to changing social demands (Freeman 1983). The main concern of the stakeholders' theory in environmental accounting is to address the environmental cost elements and its valuation. Konar and Cohen (2001) examine the extent to which a firm's environmental performance is represented in market-value movements of their stocks. Their study provides a significant added-value to the literature, as it extends the standard economic technique of decomposing a firm's

market value into the components of tangible and intangible assets. This is done by filtering the intangible environmental part out of the total intangible asset value. The authors find that there is a significant positive relationship between a firm's environmental performance and the intangible asset value of a sample taken from the S&P 500. Furthermore, the empirical findings suggest that major corporations "voluntarily over comply" with environmental regulations in order to externally portray a healthy environmental image. Yet, the authors fail to prove whether this relationship is truly causal and leads to the positive significance of the relationship of the variables.

Legitimacy Theory. (Dowling and Pfeffer in 1975)

The Legitimacy theory was propounded by Dowling and Pfeffer in 1975. This theory states that organizations seek to operate within what is considered acceptable in the society. What is considered as acceptable behavior changes overtime and the firm must be prepared for variations in the environment taking ethical aspects into account. Legitimacy may also be seen as a generalized perception or assumption that the action of an entity is desirable, proper or appropriate within some society constructed system of norms, values, beliefs and definitions. Legitimacy theory offers a powerful mechanism for understanding voluntary social and environmental disclosure made by corporations, and that this understanding would provide a vehicle for engaging in critical public debate.

Empirical Framework

Akpa and Odo (2024), examined the impact of corporate social responsibility on financial performance of selected Nigerian banks, (2011-2021). This study investigated the impact of corporate social responsibility (CSR) on the financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria operating in the international market. Some of the specific objectives of the study are to examine the impact of Corporate Social Responsibility on the net profit margin of Nigeria banks operating in the international market and also on the return on equity of Nigeria banks operating in the international market. Longitudinal panel research design was adopted for this study. Using panel data of 8 commercial banks in Nigeria operating in the international market from 2011 to 2021, Pooled OLS regression was employed to test the impact of CSR on financial performance. The results show a positive impact of CSR on net profit margin, indicating that CSR initiatives positively affect the financial performance of commercial banks in Nigeria operating in the international market. Similarly, there was a significant impact of CSR on return on equity, implying that commercial banks in Nigeria operating in the international market that prioritize CSR activities tend to have higher returns on equity. The study contributes to the existing literature on CSR in the Nigerian banking sector by providing empirical evidence on the impact of CSR and financial performance. The findings also have important implications for policymakers and bank management in Nigeria, as they provide insights into how CSR can be used to improve the performance and reputation of Nigerian commercial banks operating in the international market.

Yoon et al., (2024), examined the corporate social responsibility and financial performance: New evidence from the Korean market. We examine how corporate social responsibility affects financial performance in the Korean market by examining a new set of data, the ESG score. Using panel regression models, we show that the ESG score is negatively related with widely used measures of financial performance, ROA and Tobin's Q, unlike extant studies arguing for the positive relationships. Among the three pillars of ESG performance, the social and governance scores robustly show negative relationships with ROA but the environmental score does not. The consideration of unique Korean governance structure, *chaebol*, does not change our findings. Our findings generally support the traditional view of corporations but argue against the stakeholder theory.

Ukpe et al., (2024), examine corporate social responsibility disclosure and financial performance of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The disclosure of CSR activities has gained significant attention as a means for organizations to demonstrate their commitment to ethical business practices. In view of this, this study examined the effect of corporate social responsibility disclosure & financial performance of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Ex-post facto research design was adopted, and panel data covering ten (10) years (2013-2022) were collected across twelve (12) firms listed in industrial goods sector in Nigeria which formed the sample size of the study. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and multiple linear regression analysis via E-views 10.0 statistical package. The study findings included that community responsibility disclosure has a positive significant relationship (Coeff. = 0.0305{0.0047}) with return on equity of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria while philanthropic responsibility disclosure has an insignificant negative relationship (Coeff. = -0.2898{0.0608}) with return on equity of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. It also revealed that social responsibility disclosure has a positive significant relationship (Coeff. = 0.2103{0.0165}) with return on equity of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Hence, it was concluded that strong commitment to CSR disclosure exhibits exceptional financial performance. The study recommended, amongst others, that companies should reevaluate philanthropic initiatives to ensure they align with corporate strategy and positively impact financial performance.

Ime et al., (2024) empirically examined corporate social responsibility disclosures and cost of capital of listed pharmaceutical firms in Nigeria. Noticeable gap exists when the company focuses on their financial bottom lines at the expense of the environment and society where they operate. This study therefore examined the effect of corporate social responsibility disclosures on cost of capital of pharmaceutical firms listed on the floor of Nigeria Exchange Group from 2013 to 2022. This study specifically examined the effect of environmental responsibility, indigenous venture support and staff welfare disclosures on weighted average cost of capital of seven listed pharmaceutical firms in Nigeria. Ex post facto research design was used, secondary data used were analyzed using ordinary least square regression technique and the statistical package employed was SPSS version 20. The findings of this study revealed that environmental responsibility disclosures have an insignificant but positive effect on weighted average cost of capital while indigenous venture supports and staff welfare disclosures have significant negative effect on weighted average cost of capital of listed pharmaceutical firms in Nigeria. Based on these findings, it was concluded that firms that engage and disclose their corporate social responsibility initiatives would have improved financial performance through reduction in cost of capital. Thus, it was recommended that management of pharmaceutical firms should actively support

Kantudu et al., (2023) studied corporate social responsibility disclosure and value of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria: The moderating effect of foreign ownership. This study examines the moderating effect of foreign ownership on the relationship between corporate social responsibility disclosure and the value of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. This study adopted an explanatory research design to achieve this objective using secondary data collected from annual reports and accounts of the sampled companies for four years (2018-2021). The study employs multiple regression using panel-corrected standard error (PCSE) to analyze data for the study. Findings indicate that corporate social responsibility disclosure has a positive significant impact on firm value. Results also revealed that foreign ownership has a positive but insignificant impact on firm value. Furthermore, on the interaction effect of foreign ownership on the relationship between corporate social responsibility disclosure and firm value, the result indicates that foreign ownership has moderated the relationship between corporate social responsibility disclosure and the value of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria by strengthening the existing relationship. The findings of this study encourage more investment from foreign investors to increase the disclosure of CSR to enhance the value of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Finally, the study recommends that the management of listed oil and gas companies should diversify to attract more foreign investors to improve the value of their companies.

Olorunnisola and Usman, (2023) examined the effect of corporate social responsibility disclosure index on firm performance of selected sectorial industries in Nigeria. Descriptive statistics, Correlation regression panel and cross section analyses were adopted for the purpose of this study. The findings revealed that firms in Nigeria are yet to significantly use CSR to promote their performances like what is done by firms in developed economies. Therefore, as part of the recommendation from this study, Nigerian firms are advised to pay more attention to being CSR responsible and find ways by which this can translate to improved profit and enhancement of their overall performances.

Bhuiyan et al., (2022) study corporate social responsibility (CSR) practices in Islamic banks of Bangladesh. Corporate social responsibility (CSR) influences an organization in deciding its ethical approaches in the corporate practices and also important to maintain sustainable development. Islamic banks are capturing almost 40% of the total bank account holders in Bangladesh and contributing to the socio-economic and environmental development of the country through their CSR activities. The purpose of this paper is to investigate the impacts of CSR activities of Islamic banks for sustainable development in Bangladesh from the perception of the beneficiaries. This study is based on a questionnaire survey of 200 conveniently selected beneficiaries from five purposively selected Islamic banks in Bangladesh. Respondents' agreement score for various CSR-related activities has been observed in a five-point Likert scale and, finally, to identify the impact of CSR, exploratory factor analysis has been done. Results revealed that respondents are expressing strong agreement for almost all the activities, and they are much satisfied with ongoing CSR activities by Islamic banks, which implies positive attitudes of beneficiaries regarding CSR activities. The results of factor analysis further confirm the perception of respondents toward CSR activities of Islamic banks in terms of social enhancement, education and health, socio-economic well-being and contemporary arts and culture. The Islamic banks should enhance their CSR activities for socio-economic development, provide more allocation in education programs, and increase sponsorship in sports events and assist in flourishing Bangladeshi arts and culture.

Gull et al., (2023), examined revisiting the association between environmental performance and financial performance. In this study, we re-examine the nexus of environmental performance and financial performance by benchmarking firms relative to their industry peers based on environmental performance in a given year to identify

best-in-class and worst-in-class firms. After correcting for distributional issues while using environmental performance scores (i.e., clustering scores around the median and material differences within industries and time) and financial performance ratios (i.e., the potential impact of extreme values), we find that best-in-class firms exhibit higher financial performance than their industry peers (i.e., worst-in-class and average firms). Our findings are robust to alternative measures of environmental performance (i.e., sub dimensions of environmental performance) and financial performance. Finally, our results are robust to different identification strategies. Our findings present important and timely policy implications for firms, ESG fund managers and investors.

Gupta and Das (2022), revealed multidimensional corporate social responsibility disclosure and financial performance. The emergence of various Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) disclosure laws around the globe, in the past decade, indicates the significance of CSR for a country as well as for an organization. Organization belief CSR as a strategic tool for enhancing value, still evidence on how CSR disclosure affects financial performance has been inconclusive. To resolve the ambiguity presence in the literature, this study carried out a meta-analytic investigation based on 168 effect sizes from 73 empirical studies. This study employs a multivariate framework to explore the potential moderators that leads to conflicting results among the focal relationship of the study. The study discovers that if CSR disclosure strategy and measurement technique are adequately addressed with the help of econometric tools, then the true effect of CSR can be observed. Moreover, implications are drawn for academicians and practitioners interested in exploring the relationship between CSR disclosure and financial performance.

Kabir and Chowdhury (2022), examine the empirical analysis of the corporate social responsibility and financial performance causal nexus: Evidence from the banking sector of Bangladesh. In a culture like Bangladesh where social trust is low and corporate philanthropy is rare, corporate social responsibility (CSR) engagements of the banking sector have been in a conspicuously upward trend. It begs the question of whether the galvanization of CSR expenditure is validated by financial motivations or a genuine thirst for corporate philanthropy. The literature on the relationship between CSR and corporate financial performance (CFP) is without any overarching consensus. From an emotional viewpoint, we revere corporate philanthropy without necessarily analyzing its financial merits. This study extends the contemporary CSR literature horizon by examining 30 listed banks in Bangladesh from the years 2006 through 2018, with particular emphasis on methodology that attempts to validate the CSR-CFP relationship. In addition to examining the bidirectional causality between CSR and financial returns using Panel Vector Auto regression, the study examines the factor determinants of CSR. The study finds that better CFP leads to more CSR expenditure, but CSR expenditure does not necessarily influence CFP. Moreover, net income, total deposits, return on asset, and previous years CSR have a significant positive relationship with CSR whereas firm age has a significant negative relationship.

Bencik, (2022) ingestigated the impact of corporate social responsibility on financial performance in the era of pandemic base on Indonesian context. We use quantitative method using regression analysis. Secondary data have been collected for 36 companies in consumption industry listed in Indonesian Stock Exchange for the period of 2019-2021 which are the challenging years. We measure the disclosure of social responsibility using the global reporting index in the company's annual report. For financial performance variables, we use return on asset, return on equity and Tobin's Q, to see the consistency of the result. For the control variables, we use leverage and total asset. We found that corporate social responsibility disclosure consistently has a significant positive effect on return on asset; return on equity and for the value of Tobin's Q. The corporate social responsibility in this study is assessed using personal judgment based on the Global Reporting Initiative social responsibility disclosure indicators. This proves that especially in the era of pandemic, nonfinancial information like corporate social responsibility disclosure is very powerful for the success of the company in the case of Indonesian context. This research was conducted using period when the company faced crisis that was different from previous economic crisis. Another consideration is about global pressure related to the issue of the impact of climate change. The result of this study will contribute to whether there is consistency in the findings when tested during pandemic crisis compared to the economic situation before pandemic.

Olaniyan et al., (2021) examined the impact of corporate social responsibility on financial performance in Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to mediate the role of ethical social responsibility and its impact on the financial performance of the Nigerian manufacturing company. This study is predicated on the stakeholder theory, managerial theory, utilitarian theory and rational theory. Primary data sources were explored in presenting the facts of the situation. This paper investigates how the relationship between corporate social responsibility and employee performance affect the financial performance of manufacturing firms. The upshots of the analysis, using structural equation modelling on 150 completed questionnaires sent to the manufacturing companies in Nigeria, suggest that ethical social responsibility is significantly associated with the incorporation of corporate social responsibility through employee performance, which in turn has a significant and positive impact on financial performance. The

results contribute to previous studies that have found reliable results on the direct association between ethical social responsibility and financial performance by demonstrating that employee performance acts as a mediator in the relationship between ethical social liabilities together with the financial performance of the corporation. Managers can strengthen their stakeholder relations and ultimately improve their financial performance if ethical social responsibility to stakeholders is integrated into business routines.

Jiang et al., (2021) empirically examined the moderating role of CSR in board gender diversity and firm financial performance: Empirical evidence from an emerging economy. The current study aims to investigate the moderating role of corporate social responsibility (CSR) in board gender diversity and firm financial performance. We used the panel data regression (fixed effect) in our analysis to check the moderating role of CSR in the board gender diversity and the firm financial performance. We collected the data of Chinese listed companies from the Shenzhen and Shanghai stock exchanges from the China stock market and accounting research (CSMAR) database. We used a two-stage least square (TSLS) regression model to control the possible problem of endogeneity. Our results show that higher representation of female directors in the board is positively related to firm financial performance and that CSR has a significantly positive effect when moderating the relation between board gender diversity and firm financial performance. Besides, three control variables (board size, board member average age, and Big4) have a positive impact on the firm performance, having the leverage variable a negative impact on the firm performance. Our findings hold for a set of robustness tests. This study has important implications, namely by enriching the existing literature on CSR and by highlighting the importance of board gender diversity, and emphasizing the importance of the reporting of more CSR activities and its impact on the decision-making process.

Emamoke and Omodero, (2021) explored the impact of corporate social responsibility on profit after tax, earnings per share and net asset per share of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The study adopted ex-post facto research design. Data were collected from financial reports of five listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria for a period of 5 years from 2015 to 2019. The financial reports and the hypotheses were statistically analyzed using the panel data regression analysis. The results revealed a positive but insignificant effect of corporate social responsibility on profit after tax, earnings per share and net asset per share. According to the findings of the study, corporate social responsibility requires more attention and commitment from corporations because it ensures benefits other than profits which in the end boost financial performance.

Basiru, (2021) investigated the relationship between CSR and firm performance, as an indicator for corporate socially responsible behavior, and corporate market performance of listed companies on the Amman stock exchange (ASE). The study adopts a quantitative methodology and utilizes pooled data sets that was collected following content analysis approach of the annual reports for the period 2014 to 2019. The study sample consists of 42 listed companies. The study ran a multiple regression model in order to capture the relationship between the independent variable CSR and the dependent variable that is Firm performance which was measured using Tobin's Q. The study also utilized five control variables in order to control the hypothesized relationship between CSR and Firm Performance. The results indicate a negative but significant relationship between CSR and corporate market performance measured by Tobin's Q. The results stand against the notion of the business case for CSR, and indicate the opposite position, so, the higher CSR, the lower will be Tobin's Q. Such results support the notion of the institutional theory, and provide an initial evidence for legitimacy seeking behavior in Jordanian companies. However, the results indicate a lower level of awareness of CSR across investors and market players, which support arguments of the difference in market perceptions towards CSR.

Campbell, (2021) examined the impact of corporate social responsibility disclosure on corporate financial performance in banks, diversified financials, and insurance sectors in the Colombo Stock Exchange in Sri Lanka. The entire population was selected as the sample and it was ended with 71 companies. The required data were extracted from the annual reports of the sample companies for the period from 2015 to 2019. Corporate social responsibility disclosure was used as the independent variable which was measured by using an index with the dichotomous method, developed by using 40 items of Global Reporting Initiative G4 Guidelines. A similar index was used by prior scholars for this research area. Corporate financial performance was measured both by return on assets and return on equity and was used as the dependent variable of the present study. Moreover, firm size and leverage were used as the control variables of the study. The study executed descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation analysis, and regression analysis on panel data. The results of the analyses affirmed that corporate social responsibility disclosure has a positive impact on corporate financial performance. Furthermore, firm size and leverage reported a positive impact on return on assets where as an insignificant impact on return on equity. The current finding suggests that companies need to pay attention to make compliance with corporate social responsibility activities when configuring the strategic policy of the companies which assists in the financial success

of the companies. It might be worthwhile to replicate the study using a larger sample so that the finding could be generalized.

Cao et al., (2021) investigated the relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) disclosure and financial performance with the consideration of the mediating role of financial statement comparability (FSC) for a sample of Vietnamese listed firms. We used content analysis of the information related to the GRI Standards on annual reports in order to construct CSR disclosure score. We used a dataset of 1125 firm-year observations, covering 225 firms listed on Vietnam's stock market in the period 2014-2018. Applying OLS and GMM estimation methods, Sobel test, and using different proxies of the mediator variable to increase the robustness, we obtained two remarkable conclusions. First, CSR disclosure has a positive impact on the financial performance of listed companies in Vietnam. Second, there is a complementary mediation effect of financial statement comparability in the above relationship. Our results suggest that it is necessary to develop a legal framework for the practice and disclosure of CSR as well as to apply the international accounting standards in the Vietnamese stock market.

Rathnasooriya and Swarnapali, (2021) examined the impact of corporate social responsibility disclosure on corporate financial performance in banks, diversified financials. And insurance sectors in the Colombo Stock Exchange in Sri Lanka. The entire population was selected as the sample and it was ended with 71 companies. The required data were extracted from the annual reports of the sample companies for the period from 2015 to 2019, corporate social responsibility disclosure was used as the independent variable which was measured by using an index with the dichotomous method, developed by using 40 items of Global Reporting Initiative G4 Guidelines. A similar index was used by prior scholars for this research area. Corporate financial performance was measured both by return on assets and return on equity and was used as the dependent variable of the present study. Moreover, firm size and leverage were used as the control variables of the study. The study executed descriptive statistics. Pearson correlation analysis, and regression analysis on panel data. The results of the analyses affirmed that corporate social responsibility disclosure has a positive impact on corporate financial performance. Furthermore, firm size and leverage reported a positive impact on return on assets where as an insignificant impact on return on equity. The current finding suggests that companies need to pay attention to make compliance with corporate social responsibility activities when configuring the strategic policy of the companies which assists in the financial success of the companies. It might be worthwhile to replicate the study using a larger sample so that the finding could be generalized.

Albitar et al., (2020) x-rayed the ESG disclosure and firm performance before and after IR: The moderating role of governance mechanisms. This paper aims to investigate the effect of environmental, social and governance disclosure (ESGD) on firm performance (FP) before and after the introduction of integrated reporting (IR) further to exploring a potential moderation effect of corporate governance mechanisms on this relationship. Ordinary least squares and firm-fixed effects models were estimated based on data related to FTSE 350 between 2009 and 2018. The data has been mainly collected from Bloomberg and Capital IQ. This analysis was supplemented with applying a two-stage least squares (2 SLS) model to address any concerns regarding the expected occurrence of endogeneity problems. The results show a positive and significant relationship between ESGD score and FP before and after 2013, among a sample of FTSE 350. Furthermore, the study is suggestive of a moderation effect of corporate governance mechanisms (i.e. ownership concentration, gender diversity and board size) on the ESGD-FP nexus. Additionally, this paper finds that firms voluntarily associated with IR have a tendency to achieve better firm financial performance. The findings of the present study have several policy and practitioner implications. For example, managers may engage in ESGD to enhance their firms' financial performance by the voluntary involvement in IR, which believed to help investors to rationalize their investment decisions. Likewise, the results reiterate the crucial need to integrate more social, environmental and economic regulations to promote sustainability in the UK. The paper also offers a systematic picture for policymakers in the UK as well as future researchers. The findings of this paper indicate that IR plays a significant role in the relationship between ESGD and FP, where IR firms seemed to be achieving better FP as compared with their non-IR counterparts. This implies that stakeholders may have played a magnificent effort to encourage firms' voluntary engagement in IR in the UK.

Alwaysheh et al. (2020), studied on the relation between corporate social responsibility and financial performance. This study re-examines the relation between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and financial performance by benchmarking firms against industry peers in a given year to identify *best-in-class* and *worst-in-class* firms. We also address distributional issues when using CSR ratings (clustering of CSR scores around the median and material differences across industries and time) and financial performance ratios (the possible influence of extreme values). We find that the *best-in-class* firms outperform their industry peers in terms of operating performance and have higher relative market valuations (Tobin's Q). When we control for endogeneity, we find that the significant relation

between operating performance and CSR categories disappears, calling into question whether this relation is causal. However, we continue to find that *best-in-class* firms receive higher relative market valuations than industry peers.

Franco et al., (2020), studied on are you good enough? CSR, quality management and corporate financial performance in the hospitality industry. Hospitality firms are increasingly investing in corporate social responsibility (CSR) to generate strong relationships with stakeholders while aiming to benefit their own performance. However, CSR may bring both costs and benefits to the focal firm. We analyze how corporate financial performance (CFP) is affected by CSR, finding that the impact of CSR on CFP has a U-shaped form, where CSR is a cost that translates into higher benefits only when it generates solid relationships between firms and their stakeholders. Furthermore, we adopt a contingency approach, assessing the role of quality management (QM) on the CSR-CFP relationship. We find that the simultaneous implementation of CSR and QM is less beneficial to CFP than the isolated implementation of CSR due to the redundancy of different activities aimed at similar goals, i.e., stakeholders' satisfaction. In doing so, we advance academic understanding of the impact of CSR and QM on CFP.

Jang and Ardichvili (2020), examined the role of HRD in CSR and sustainability: A content analysis of corporate responsibility reports. This study aims to examine the role of human resource development (HRD) in corporate social responsibility (CSR) and sustainability initiatives of multinational companies (MNCs). The authors analyze contents of corporate responsibility (CR) reports disclosed by 23 MNCs from Europe, Asia and North America to examine HRD's contribution to CSR and sustainability, with particular attention to long-term human development and organization development. The analysis of CR reports indicates that HRD is perceived as playing a role in the following areas: diversity, equity and inclusion; community engagement; work-life balance; employee long-term growth and development; performance management; business ethics and ethical culture; and raising CSR awareness. In all areas, HRD was identified as playing a significant role in supporting companies' CSR agendas.

Javed et al., (2020) examined the effects of corporate social responsibility on corporate reputation and firm financial performance: Moderating role of responsible leadership. Drawing on stakeholder theory and contingency theory, this study examines the effects of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) on corporate reputation and financial performance of Pakistani firms with a moderating role of responsible leadership. Perceptual data on CSR, reputation, and performance were collected from 224 senior-level Pakistani managers through a questionnaire survey. Structural equation modeling was used to analyze the data. The results reveal that socially responsible initiatives for disparate stakeholders significantly and positively influence corporate reputation and financial performance. Moreover, CSR-reputation and CSR-performance direct relationships were found to be negatively moderated by responsible leadership. It suggests that when socially responsible firms have leaders with strong stakeholder values, they practice excessive CSR that hurts performance.

Long et al., (2020) Corporate social responsibility and financial performance: The roles of government intervention and market competition. Incorporating instrumental and political views of corporate social responsibility (CSR), this study examines the relationship between CSR and corporate financial performance in China's unique institutional context, which is featured by the coexistence of a strong government and a transitional market economy. Our results show that (a) CSR positively affects financial performance, (b) state ownership weakens the relationship between CSR and financial performance, and (c) industry competition strengthens the relationship between CSR and financial performance for both state-owned and non-state-owned firms. This study reveals that, although both an instrumental view and a political view of CSR are applicable in China, the motivation to create economic benefits for firms dominates, and market competition increases the strategic use of CSR.

Saha et al., (2020) examine the effect of ethical leadership and corporate social responsibility on firm performance: A systematic review. This study provides empirical evidence on the association between board attributes and corporate social responsibility (CSR) engagement as well as between CSR engagement and corporate performance—in the global energy sector. The data for the period of 2011–2018 was obtained from Thomson Reuters. The results indicate that board diligence and CSR committees are robust drivers of CSR performance, as peroxide by the composite environmental, social, and governance (ESG) score along with its three individual indicators. While board independence is more influential in boosting the aggregate ESG score and the governance indicator, the board's gender diversity is more influential in environmental and governance indicators. However, higher CSR performance does not guarantee higher financial performance—as peroxide by both market and accounting performance. We provide theoretical and practical implications, to guide regulators and energy firms in ensuring the sustainable development of the sector.

Zhao et al. (2020), examined perception of corporate hypocrisy in China: The roles of corporate social responsibility implementation and communication. In the past two decades, corporate hypocrisy has become a phenomenon that cannot be ignored in Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) practice (Wagner et al., 2009) and has thus become a concern for management scholars (Cho and Lee, 2019). Using smart PLS, based on attribution theory, this paper

takes 28 Chinese listed enterprises as examples to explore the influence of CSR motivation on its communication and implementation, as well as the impact of CSR implementation and promotion on consumers' perception of corporate hypocrisy. The research finds a negative correlation between value-driven motivation and corporate hypocrisy and a positive correlation of performance-driven motivation and stakeholder-driven motivation with corporate hypocrisy. The theoretical contribution of this paper is mainly reflected in the following four aspects. (1) It describes the scale of CSR implementation research and enriches the measurement tools of CSR implementation. (2) It enriches and expands research results in the field of CSR motivation perception. From the perspective of CSR and attribution theory, this study explores the influence of consumers' perception of CSR motivation on CSR communication and CSR implementation. (3) It supplements research results in the field of corporate hypocrisy. The influence of CSR communication and CSR implementation on corporate hypocrisy is clarified. (4) It clarifies the impact of CSR communication on CSR implementation so as to help enterprises better match CSR communication strategy and CSR implementation in practice and reduce consumers' perception of corporate hypocrisy. It is suggested that enterprises find their own positioning on CSR motivation, which provides a reference with which enterprises can make better decisions on CSR communication strategy after implementing CSR behavior and provides empirical evidence for the research on CSR motivation perception and corporate hypocrisy in China.

Malik and Okere (2020) evaluated the relationship between corporate social responsibility, environmental investments and financial performance: evidence from manufacturing companies. The study made use of panel regression analysis and descriptive analysis to expand on the variables applied. The study's population comprised the total sixty-four (64) manufacturing companies. The study data spanned from a period of eight years, i.e.. From 2011 to 2018. The research used donations, employee benefits and staff training cost as the self-determining variables and monetary output as the reliant factor. From empirical analyses, the study found out that there was a positive and significant relationship between environmental investments and financial performance of Nigerian manufacturing firms.

Falaye (2020) evaluated the relationship between corporate social responsibilities. Environmental investments and financial performance: evidence from manufacturing companies. The study made use of panel regression analysis and descriptive analysis to expand on the variables applied. The study's population comprised the total sixty-four (64) manufacturing companies. The study data spanned from a period of eight years, i.e.. from 2011 to 2018. The research used donations, employee benefits and staff training cost as the self-determining variables and monetary output as the reliant factor. From empirical analyses, the study found out that there was a positive and significant relationship between environmental investments and financial performance of Nigerian manufacturing firms.

Iswati, (2020) obtain empirical evidence about the effect of sustainability reporting and corporate social responsibilities on firm value with mediation of financial performance to 132 manufacturing companies listed on Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) in 2017-2018. This study is quantitative research by testing hypotheses because it uses statistical methods to resolve the problem. Data Analyzed using multiple linear regression model to examine the impact of the disclosure of sustainability reporting and the disclosure of corporate social responsibility toward firm value with the mediation of financial performance Results: The findings of this study indicate that the disclosure of sustainability reporting and corporate social responsibility do not affect financial performance. The disclosure of sustainability reporting and corporate social responsibility do not affect firm value. The Firm performance affects firm value. The Firm performance does not mediate the relationship of corporate social responsibility disclosure to firm value and the relationship of disclosure of sustainability reporting to firm value. This study uses stakeholder theory as the basis to explain how to minimize gap between managers who run companies and stakeholders who have high expectation toward corporates performance and legitimacy theory that can be used as a vehicle to construct corporate strategy, especially related to efforts to position them in an increasingly advanced society.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research adopts the ex-post facto research design because the study relied on historical accounting data obtained from audited annual reports of the sampled manufacturing firms and the researchers do not intend to manipulate the data. Also, this design is adopted because the researcher cannot manipulate the data obtained. This study anchor on two (2) sectors comprising of 34 manufacturing firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group consistently from 2014 to 2023. The two sectors selected for this study were as presented in table 3.1 below.

Table 3.1 Population of the study

S / N	S E C T O R	NO. OF FIRMS
1	I n d u s t r i a l g o o d s	1 3
2	C o n s u m e r g o o d s	2 1
TOTAL		34

Source: Researcher’s conceptualization, (2024)

A sample size of twenty-five (25) manufacturing firms listed on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group was purposively selected for the study. This was however subjected to a validity test using Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) formula. The Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) formula is given as follows;

$$n \geq 50 + 8(m)$$

Where;

n = number of pooled observations

m = number of predictor variables, i.e 4.

50+8(m) = minimum number of pooled observations

Therefore, $n \geq 50 + 8(4)$

$$n \geq 82$$

Consequently, considering four (4) explanatory variables for this study, the minimum number of pooled observations for this study stood at 82 while the number of pooled observations with a sample size of twenty-five (25) is 250 (i.e 25 by 10). Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting the required sample. Purposive sampling involves selecting specific firms based on predetermined criteria, allowing the researcher to focus on particular characteristics relevant to the study. For this study, availability of data served as the yardstick for selection because of accuracy. The secondary source of data was used for this study. The data was obtained via audited annual reports of relevant companies listed on the floor of the Nigerian Group Exchange website. The data was analyzed using the multiple regression models with the aid of E-Views Version 10.0. Regression analysis is a statistical process for estimating the relationships among variables. It can be used to assess the strength of the relationship between variables and for making predictions based on the observed input data. Regression analysis helps us to understand the relationship between a dependent (target) variable and one or more independent (explanatory) variables. The method of Ordinary Least Square (OLS) of multiple regression technique was used in the analysis of the study.

The model used in this study is based on the description of the effect of the predictor on the criterion variable of this research work. In other words, the multiple linear regression model is adopted. It is given as:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \mu \dots\dots\dots\text{equation 1.}$$

Where;

Y = Financial Performance (dependent variable)

X = Corporate Social Responsibility (explanatory/independent variable)

Explicitly, the equation was defined as:

$$\text{Financial Performance} = f(\text{Corporate Social Responsibility}) + \mu$$

Therefore, the broad model for this study was modified as;

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1ENR_{it} + \beta_2SR_{it} + \beta_3ER_{it} + \beta_4SW + \mu_{it} \dots\dots\dots\text{equation 2.}$$

Where;

ROA_{it} = Return on Assets of firm *i* in period *t*

ENR_{it} = Environmental Responsibility of firm *i* in period *t*

SR_{it} = Social Responsibility of firm *i* in period *t*

ER_{it} = Economic Responsibility of firm *i* in period *t*

SW = Staff Welfare Responsibility of firm *i* in period *t*

β₀ = Intercept or regression constant

β₁, β₂ β₃ β₄ = Regression coefficients to be estimated for firm *i* in period *t*

μ = Stochastic error term.

Table 3.2 Operationalization of variables

Concept	Proxy	Measurement	Source
Corporate social responsibility (Independent variable)	Environmental Responsibility	Natural log of total Environmental remediation cost.	Olayinka and Temitope (2011)
	Social Responsibility	Natural Log of donations made	Olayinka and Temitope (2011)
	Economic Responsibility	Natural Log of taxes paid	Olayinka and Temitope (2011)
	Staff Welfare Responsibility	Natural Log of employees' expenses	Olayinka and Temitope (2011)
Financial performance (Dependent variable)	Return on asset	Profit after tax /total asset employed	Olayinka and Temitope (2011)

Source: Researcher's conceptualization (2024)

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Data presentation

The data comprise a panel data of two hundred and fifty (250) pooled observations gathered across twenty-five (25) listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria over ten (10) years-period (2014-2023). The data include the dependent variable – Return on Asset and the independent variables which were environmental responsibility (ENR), social responsibility (SR), economic responsibility (ER) and staff welfare responsibility (SW) of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Data analysis

Various statistical techniques were utilized in the analysis of data presented in table 4.1 (see Appendix II). These include descriptive statistics, regression assumption tests and panel multiple regression analysis. The results from the panel multiple regression analysis were used in the testing of the research hypotheses which had been stated in the first section of this work.

Descriptive statistics

This was conducted to understand the behaviour of the data using various statistics including mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis. The result for the descriptive statistics analysis is as presented in table 4.2 below;

Table 4.2 Descriptive Statistics of the variables

	ROA	ENR	SR	ER	SW
Mean	0.031767	5.431829	6.052171	2.778977	5.765265
Median	0.035100	5.461150	5.933875	2.931265	5.540968
Maximum	0.539594	7.919660	11.24966	8.311558	9.979660
Minimum	-0.551969	2.939660	-0.277625	-2.430418	0.949660
Std. Dev.	0.124356	0.934870	2.574422	2.414483	1.692989
Skewness	-0.425390	0.018739	0.000752	0.171443	-0.081493
Kurtosis	7.450865	2.715729	2.323380	2.000744	2.402110
Jarque-Bera	213.8961	0.856403	4.768928	11.62588	4.000382
Probability	0.000000	0.651680	0.092138	0.002989	0.135309
Sum	7.941770	1357.957	1513.043	694.7443	1441.316
Sum Sq. Dev.	3.850651	217.6216	1650.284	1451.603	713.6865
Observations	250	250	250	250	250

Source: Researcher's Computation using E-views 10.0 (2024).

Table 4.2 shows that return on asset (ROA), environmental responsibility (ENR), social responsibility (SR), economic responsibility (ER) and staff welfare responsibility (SW) had mean values of 0.03176 (3.17%), 5.43, 6.05, 2.77 and 5.76 respectively. This indicates the central or average values for these variables from 2014 to 2023. The median values obtained for return on asset (ROA), environmental responsibility (ENR), social responsibility (SR), economic responsibility and staff welfare responsibility (SW) were 0.03510 (3.51%), 5.46, 5.93, 2.93 and 5.54 respectively. These constituted the middle values for the distributions of these variables under the period covered in this study (2014 to 2023).

In terms of the level of variability and dispersion in the distribution of these variables, the standard deviations obtained for the variables: return on asset (ROA), environmental responsibility (ENR), social responsibility (SR), economic responsibility (ER) and staff welfare responsibility (SW) were 0.12, 0.93, 2.57, 2.41 and 0.94 respectively. This indicates varying levels of variability in the distribution social responsibility (ENR)

indicating high variations in the distributions. Similarly, from the skewness values obtained, return on asset (ROA) and staff welfare responsibility, showed negative while environmental responsibility (ENR), social responsibility (SR) and economic responsibility (ER) had a positive skewness values meaning they were skewed to the right. This indicates that the mean values of these variables were greater than their median and mode.

The Kurtosis values obtained for the variables [return on asset (ROA), environmental responsibility (ENR), social responsibility (SR), economic responsibility (ER)] and staff welfare responsibility (SW) were 7.45, 2.27, 2.32, 2, 2.40 respectively. Since the values of the kurtosis are greater than zero (0), it indicates a leptokurtic distribution, hence the presence of outliers in the data for the variables. Finally, based on the Jarque-Bera probability values obtained, all variables indicated normality in their distribution, given that their Jarque-Bera probability was greater than 0.05.

Model evaluation

Residual and coefficient diagnostics were however conducted to assess the suitability of the model as stated in the previous section. These include normality test, multicollinearity test, heteroscedasticity test and autocorrelation assessment.

4.2.2.1 Normality test

Fig. 4.1 Jarque-Bera Normality test results

Source: E-views 10.0 Output (2024)

The essence of a normality test is to determine if a dataset or sample follows a normal distribution. This is important because many statistical models assume normality, and deviations from normality can affect the validity of statistical inference. The Jarque-Bera test was employed in this case. As applied, if the p-value associated with the Jarque-Bera test is below a predetermined significance level ($p < 0.05$), then we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the data do not follow a normal distribution. With a p-value of 0.135330, there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the data were normally distributed.

Multicollinearity test

Table 4.3: Spearman rank correlation matrix

	ROA	ENR	SR	ER	SW
ROA	1.000000	-0.029580	0.102067	0.228722	0.193790
ENR	-0.029580	1.000000	0.082194	0.069895	-0.108218
SR	0.102067	0.082194	1.000000	-0.068901	0.263050
ER	0.228722	0.069895	-0.068901	1.000000	-0.115970
SW	0.193790	-0.108218	0.263050	-0.115970	1.000000

Source: Researcher’s computation (2024) using Eviews 10.0

The correlation analysis showed that all independent variables have coefficients of -0.029, 0.102, 0.228, 0.19 respectively, indicating weak correlations amongst each other. The correlation matrix also confirmed absence of multicollinearity as all correlation coefficients were less than 0.80.

Heteroscedasticity test

Table 4.4 Heteroscedasticity test

Test	Statistic	df.	Prob.
Breusch-Pagan LM	429.5960	300	0.0000
Pesaran scaled LM	4.270113		0.0000
Pesaran CD	-1.501247		0.1333

Source: E-views 10.0 Output (2024)

Heteroscedasticity refers to the unequal spread of residuals (or errors) across the range of predictor variables in a regression model. Heteroscedasticity tests aim to detect this violation of the assumption of constant variance. Common tests include the Breusch-Pagan test and the White test, which assess the relationship between the squared residuals and the predictor variables. The statistics and probability value associated with the Breusch-Pagan LM test otherwise known as the Breusch-Pagan Godfrey test help determine whether there is evidence of heteroscedasticity in the regression model. A low p-value ($p < 0.05$) suggests evidence against the null hypothesis in favour of the alternate hypothesis which indicates the presence of heteroscedasticity in the regression model. With a p-value of 0.0000, there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, thus, conclude that the predictor variables in the regression model were not homoscedastic.

Autocorrelation

Autocorrelation, also known as serial correlation, occurs when there is a correlation between the residual errors of a time series or panel data over time. Autocorrelation tests examine whether the residuals are independently distributed or if there is a systematic pattern of dependence. The Durbin-Watson statistic is commonly used to test for autocorrelation, with values close to 2 indicating no significant autocorrelation. The Durbin-Watson statistic as obtained from the panel regression results (see Appendix II) was utilized in this case. The Durbin-Watson statistic value of 1.888835 suggests that there is a low negative autocorrelation present in the data.

Test of hypotheses

Each of the hypotheses in this study was tested based on the result obtained from the panel multiple regression analysis. The result that relates to these hypotheses is summarized in Table 4.5 below;

Table 4.5 Panel Multiple Regression Results

Dependent Variable: ROA
 Method: Panel Least Squares
 Date: 11/23/24 Time: 19:32
 Sample: 2014 2023
 Periods included: 10
 Cross-sections included: 25
 Total panel (balanced) observations: 250

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.064354	0.057170	-3.125668	0.0000
ENR	-0.004066	0.008337	-0.487742	0.6262
SR	0.004365	0.003101	1.407720	0.1605
ER	0.007375	0.003214	2.294642	0.0226
SW	0.012366	0.004780	2.587124	0.0103
R-squared	0.560507	Mean dependent var		0.031767
Adjusted R-squared	0.545168	S.D. dependent var		0.124356
S.E. of regression	0.121515	Akaike info criterion		-1.357756
Sum squared resid	3.617660	Schwarz criterion		-1.287327
Log likelihood	174.7196	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-1.329411
F-statistic	13.44737	Durbin-Watson stat		1.888835
Prob(F-statistic)	0.004021			

Source: E-views 10.0 Output (2024)

The multiple regression line is as written below:

$$ROA = -0.0643544197587 - 0.00406617011323*ENR + 0.0043654194082*SR + 0.00737477037833*ER + 0.0123660671685*SW + \mu_1$$

Considering the regression results above, when the independent variables- environmental responsibility (ENR), social responsibility (SR) and economic responsibility (ER), the dependent variable- Return on Assets (ROA) decreased at a constant average of approximately 6.435%. However, a one percent rise in environmental responsibility (ENR), decreases return on assets by approximately 0.406% while similar variation in social responsibility (SR) and economic responsibility (ER) and staff welfare responsibility increases return on assets by approximately 0.4365%, 0.7375% and 1.2366% respectively.

Hypothesis one

Ho: Environmental responsibility has no significant effect on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

H₁: Environmental responsibility has significant effect on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

In order to test whether the variations in return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria caused by environmental responsibility is significant. The T-test was carried out at .05 significance level with Ttab of 2.059 given at $t_{0.05, 25}$. From the result in Table 4.5, the Tcal of 0.487742 is less than Ttab given at $t_{0.05, 25}$. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that Environmental responsibility has no significant effect on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria holds, thus accepted, and the alternate hypothesis rejected. The null hypothesis is further accepted given that at $t_{0.05, 25}$, its probability value (p-value = 0.6262) is greater than 0.05.

Hypothesis two

Ho: Social responsibility has no significant effect on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

H₁: Social responsibility has significant effect on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

In order to test whether the variations in return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria caused by social responsibility is significant. The T-test was carried out at .05 significance level with Ttab of 2.059 given at $t_{0.05, 25}$. From the result in Table 4.5, the Tcal of 1.407720 is less than Ttab given at $t_{0.05, 25}$. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that social responsibility has no significant effect on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria holds, thus accepted, and the alternative hypothesis rejected. The null hypothesis is further accepted given that at $t_{0.05, 25}$, its probability value (p-value = 0.1605) is greater than 0.05.

Hypothesis three

Ho: Economic responsibility has no significant effect on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

H₁: Economic responsibility has no significant effect on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

In order to test whether the variations in return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria caused by economic responsibility is significant. The T-test was carried out at .05 significance level with Ttab of 2.059 given at $t_{0.05, 25}$. From the result in Table 4.5, the Tcal of 2.2946 is greater than Ttab given at $t_{0.05, 25}$. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that economic responsibility has no significant effect on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria fails to hold, thus rejected, and the alternative hypothesis accepted. The null hypothesis is further rejected given that at $t_{0.05, 25}$, its probability value (p-value = 0.0226) is less than 0.05.

Hypothesis four

Ho: Staff welfare responsibility has no significant effect on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

H₁: Staff welfare responsibility has no significant effect on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

In addition, by way of testing whether the variations in return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria caused by economic responsibility is significant, the T-test was carried out at .05 significance level with Ttab of 2.059 given at $t_{0.05, 25}$. From the result in Table 4.5, the Tcal of 2.5871 is greater than Ttab given at $t_{0.05, 25}$. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that staff welfare responsibility has no significant effect on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria fails to hold, thus rejected, and the alternative hypothesis accepted. The null hypothesis is further rejected given that at $t_{0.05, 25}$, its probability value (p-value = 0.0103) is less than 0.05.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Environmental responsibility and return on assets

The finding that environmental responsibility has a non-significant negative effect on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria suggests that investing in environmental responsibility may not necessarily lead to an improvement in financial performance. This could be because environmental responsibility initiatives may require significant upfront investments, which may not yield immediate financial returns. Additionally, the negative coefficient, although non-significant, suggests that environmental responsibility may even have a slight negative impact on return on assets. This finding is surprising, given the growing importance of environmental sustainability in the business world. However, it may be that Nigerian manufacturing firms are not yet reaping the financial benefits of environmental responsibility, possibly due to a lack of awareness or inadequate implementation of environmental sustainability practices. Studies by Gull *et al.* (2023), and Ukpe *et al.* (2024), align with this finding as they also found mixed results on the impact of environmental responsibility on financial performance.

Social responsibility and return on assets

The finding that social responsibility has a non-significant positive effect on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria suggests that investing in social responsibility may have a slightly positive impact on financial performance, although this impact is not statistically significant. This could be because social responsibility initiatives may lead to improved brand reputation, customer loyalty, and employee morale, which can ultimately contribute to improved financial performance.

However, the non-significant coefficient suggests that the relationship between social responsibility and return on assets is not strong enough to be statistically significant. This may be because social responsibility initiatives may not be directly related to financial performance, or because the measurement of social responsibility may not be accurate or comprehensive.

Studies by Olaniyan et al. (2021), and Kabir and Chowdhury (2022), align with this finding as they found a positive relationship between social responsibility and financial performance, although the relationship was not always significant.

Economic responsibility and return on assets

The finding that economic responsibility has a significant positive effect on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria suggests that investing in economic responsibility can lead to improved financial performance. Economic responsibility refers to a firm's commitment to generating economic value for its stakeholders, including shareholders, employees, and customers. This finding suggests that firms that prioritize economic responsibility are more likely to achieve higher returns on assets.

This finding is consistent with the idea that firms that prioritize economic responsibility are more likely to be financially sustainable and successful in the long run. Economic responsibility can lead to improved financial performance by reducing costs, increasing revenue, and improving efficiency. The significant positive coefficient suggests that economic responsibility is an important driver of financial performance in Nigerian manufacturing firms. Studies by Akpa and Odo (2024), and Bencik (2022), align with this finding as they found a significant positive relationship between economic responsibility and financial performance.

Staff welfare responsibility and return on assets

The finding that staff welfare responsibility has a significant positive effect on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria suggests that investing in staff welfare can lead to improved financial performance. Staff welfare responsibility refers to a firm's commitment to providing a safe and healthy work environment, fair compensation and benefits, and opportunities for training and development. This finding suggests that firms that prioritize staff welfare are more likely to achieve higher returns on assets.

This finding is consistent with the idea that firms that prioritize staff welfare are more likely to have motivated and productive employees, which can lead to improved financial performance. Staff welfare responsibility can lead to improved financial performance by reducing turnover and absenteeism, improving productivity, and increasing employee engagement. The significant positive coefficient suggests that staff welfare responsibility is an important driver of financial performance in Nigerian manufacturing firms. Studies by Ukpe et al. (2024), and Olaniyan et al. (2021), align with this finding as they found a positive relationship between staff welfare responsibility and financial performance, and the relationship was significant in some cases.

This is the last section of this study. It summarizes the research findings, proffer suggestions and recommendations based on the research findings. It also gives an insight for further studies as well as explains how this present study contributes to the existing body of knowledge on the subject matter.

Summary of findings

This study examined the effect of corporate social responsibility on financial performance of listed manufacturing firms on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group for the period of ten (10) years; from 2014 to 2023. The independent variable (corporate social responsibility) was proxied by environmental responsibility, social responsibility, economic responsibility and staff welfare responsibility while the dependent variable (financial performance) was proxied by return on asset. Based on the analysis of data collected, the following findings were drawn.

1. Environmental responsibility has a non-significant negative effect (Coeff. =-0.0040{0.6262}) on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
2. Social responsibility has a non-significant positive effect (Coeff. =0.0043{0.1605}) on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
3. Economic responsibility has a significant positive effect (Coeff. =0.0073{0.0226}) on return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
4. Staff welfare responsibility has a significant positive effect (Coeff. =0.0123{0.0103}) on return on assets of

listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the effect of corporate social responsibility on the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria, with a focus on environmental responsibility, social responsibility, economic responsibility, and staff welfare responsibility. The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance in the Nigerian manufacturing sector. The results show that environmental responsibility has a non-significant negative effect on return on assets, while social responsibility has a non-significant positive effect. However, economic responsibility and staff welfare responsibility have significant positive effects on return on assets. These findings suggest that while some aspects of corporate social responsibility may not have a significant impact on financial performance, others can have a positive and significant impact. The implications of this study are significant for policymakers, managers, and stakeholders in the Nigerian manufacturing sector. The findings suggest that firms that prioritize economic responsibility and staff welfare responsibility are likely to experience improved financial performance. Therefore, managers and policymakers should prioritize these aspects of corporate social responsibility in order to improve financial performance and contribute to the sustainable development of the sector.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Firms should review their environmental responsibility initiatives and consider alternative approaches that may be more effective in improving financial performance.
2. Policymakers and regulatory bodies in Nigeria should encourage listed manufacturing firms to disclose their social responsibility initiatives more transparently. Improved disclosure of social responsibility initiatives can help stakeholders better understand the impact of these initiatives and make more informed investment decisions.
3. Listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria should prioritize economic responsibility in their corporate social responsibility initiatives. This can be achieved by investing in initiatives that promote economic growth, such as creating jobs, stimulating local economic development, and promoting entrepreneurship.
4. Managers of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria should invest more in staff welfare responsibility. This can be achieved by providing a safe and healthy work environment, offering competitive compensation and benefits, and promoting employee development and well-being.

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